

ASTROx Dark Sky: Integrating Astronomy Education into Interactive Classrooms

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Abstract: The urgent issue of sustainability is one that students frequently encounter in their textbooks and are aware of. However, there exists a need to go beyond traditional classroom lessons or group project presentations by incorporating sustainable practices into astronomy education. ASTROx is an interdisciplinary initiative aimed at merging astronomy with other academic subjects based on the Sustainable Development Goals. This presentation will showcase a student-led social innovation project focused on dark-sky advocacy and science communication as a solution to real-world community challenges. The students utilized various methods, including light pollution field trips, a science communication booth at social innovation festival, multimedia dark sky advocacy, outdoor classrooms, design thinking lessons, and hands-on experiences, to raise awareness about urban light pollution.

Keywords: dark sky; astronomy education; classrooms.

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